

A REVIEW ON *DODONAEA VISCOSA*

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ABSTRACT

Dodonaea viscosa belongs to the family Sapindaceae and is a common plant found in many regions throughout tropical and subtropical regions. In India, the leaves and roots of *Dodonaea viscosa* are used to treat various ailments like wounds, inflammation and infections. The plant contains various Phytoconstituents like alkaloids, glycosides, terpenoids, steroids, phenolic compounds, flavonoids and it also contains carbohydrates, proteins and fatty acids. The extract of plant possesses the following pharmacological activities like Antihelmintic, Antioxidant, Antibacterial, Antidiabetic, Anti-inflammatory, Wound healing. The main idea regarding the creation of this review paper is to

highlight the medicinal importance of different parts of the plant of *Dodonaea viscosa*.

KEYWORDS: *Dodonaea Viscosa*, Herbal Medicine, Phytochemistry, Pharmacological Activities.

INTRODUCTION

Ever since ancient times, in search for rescue for their disease, the people looked for drugs in nature.^[1] In view of the fact that at the time there was not sufficient information either concerning the reasons for the illnesses or concerning which plant and how it could be utilized as a cure, everything was based on experience. In time, the reasons for the usage of specific medicinal plants for treatment of certain diseases were being discovered thus, the medicinal plants usage gradually abandoned the empiric framework and became founded on explicatory facts. Until the advent of iatrochemistry in 16th century, plants had been the source of treatment and prophylaxis. Nonetheless, the decreasing efficacy of synthetic drugs and the increasing contraindications of their usage make the usage of natural drugs topical again.^[2] In the last few decades there has been an exponential growth in the field of herbal

medicine. It is getting popularized in developing and developed countries owing to its natural origin and lesser side effects. On the other hand, two thirds of the new chemicals identified yearly were extracted from higher plants. 75% of the world's population used plants for therapy and prevention. In the US, where chemical synthesis dominates the pharmaceutical industry, 25% of the pharmaceuticals are based on plant-derived chemicals. Plants are a valuable source of a wide range of secondary metabolites, which are used for therapeutic purposes. The chemical analysis of *Dodonaea viscosa* (Sapindaceae), revealed that the plant contained alkaloids, flavonoids, fixed oil, fat, steroids, phenolics, saponins, tannins, gums, mucilage, carbohydrates, reducing sugar, glycosides and trace elements. The pharmacological studies showed that *Dodonaea viscosa* possessed Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial, Insecticidal, Antioxidant, Cytotoxic, Antifertility, Wound healing, Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic, Antiulcer, Antispasmodic, Anti-diarrheal and Detoxification effects. This review will shed some light on the chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Dodonaea viscosa*.^[3]

Fig no.1: *Dodonaea viscosa* plant.

SYNONYMS^[4]

Kannada: Bandarike, Bandru.

Hindi: Sanatta.

English: Hop bush.

TAXONOMY^[5]

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum : Tracheophyta

Order : Sapandales

Class : Magnoliopsida

Family : Sapandaceae

Genus : *viscosa*

Species : *Dodonaea viscosa*

DISTRIBUTION

The center of origin of *Dodonaea viscosa* is believed to be Australia, but it occurs throughout the tropics and subtropics. The plant is distributed in **Africa** (Kenya; Tanzania; Uganda, Ethiopia, Somalia, Sudan, Angola, Malawi, Mozambique, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Botswana, South Africa, Ghana, Nigeria, Senegal, Togo, Cameroon, Zaire, Madagascar, Mauritius, Reunion, Seychelles).

Asia (Saudi Arabia, China, Japan, Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines). **Australia** (Australasia, New Zealand); **Northern America** (Mexico, United States). **Southern America** (Brazil, Bahamas, Bermuda, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guadeloupe, Haiti, Jamaica, Martinique, Puerto Rico, Trinidad and Tobago, Suriname, Venezuela, Argentina, Chile, Uruguay, Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru).^[6]

MORPHOLOGY

Seeds^[7]

Seeds are sub globose, dark chocolate brown to black in color and around 3- 4 mm in diameter. The seeds are hard coated and plugged at the micropyle. The seed coat is said to be impervious to water. Burrows reported seeds to measure 3.1 ± 0.09 mm in length and 2.3 ± 0.14 mm in width.

Fig no. 2: Seeds of *Dodonaea viscosa*.

Endosperm is consumed in mature seeds. Pleurogram also present. Seeds are glutinous (viscid shiny and sticky surface). They are lustrous and devoid of non-glandular hairs but dot ted

with resin glands of various sizes. Testa surface in low magnification appears as 'ripples in the water' in relief but in higher magnification the epidermal cells are periclinally concave. The anticlinal walls are thick, smooth and curvy.

Leaves^[8]

Color - Upper surface dark green and lower surface pale green.

Size - 3.8 to 10 cm (l) and 0.6 to 3.9 cm.

Form - Simple, lanceolate, acute at both ends and narrowed to distinct petiole, stipulate, Symmetrical base, mid rib prominent with closely arranged lateral nerves.

Venation – pinnately parallel.

Fig no. 3: Leaves of Dodonaea viscosa.

Stems and Branches^[7]

Young stems are reddish or purplish and often hairy.

Older stems become woody and smooth.

Flowers^[7]

Type - Unisexual (dioecious-male and female flowers on separate plants).

Arrangement - Small clusters in axillary panicles or cyme Color- Greenish yellow to purplish.

Male Flowers - 8 stamens, no ovary.

Female Flowers – Ovary 3-4 celled; styles are short and branched.

Fig no 4: Flowers of *Dodonaea viscosa*.

Fruits^[7]

Type - Papery winged capsule.

Size – About 1 to 2 cm across.

Shape - 2 to 4 winged.

Color – Green when immature and turning reddish, pink, or purplish brown when mature.

Dispersal- Wind dispersed due to winged structure.

MICROSCOPY

LEAF^[9]

1. Epidermis

- Upper and lower epidermis are single layered, composed of polygonal cells
- Covered with cuticle, sometimes thickened.
- Stomata is present on both surfaces but more on the lower surface.
- Trichomes are glandular and non-glandular types which are short, multicellular, uniseriate.

2. Mesophyll

- **Palisade cells:** 1to 2 layers beneath the upper epidermis which is completely arranged.
- **Spongy parenchyma:** Loosely arranged with air spaces, containing chloroplasts.

3. Vascular Bundle

- Located centrally in the midrib.
- It is bilateral.

PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS^[10]

The isolation and characterization of several flavonoids, diterpenoid acids, some biologically active saponins and plant acids, sterols and tannins from the aerial parts of *Dodonaea viscosa*.

COMMON NAME	CHEMICAL NAMES
Aliarin	5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3'- (3hydroxymethylbutanol) 3,6- dimethoxyflavone
Pinocembrin	5,7-dihydroxyflavanone
Penduletin	5,4'-Dihydroxy-3,6,7- Trimethoxy flavone
Viscosol	3'-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)-5,7- dihydroxy-3,6,4'-trimethoxy flavone
Sakuranetin	(S)-5,4'-dihydroxy-7- methoxyflavone
Isokaempferide	3,5,7,4'-Tetrahydroxyl-3'- methoxyflavone
Ermanin	3,5,7,4'-Tetrahydroxyl-3,4'- dimethoxyflavone
Cirsimaritin	5, 4'-Dihydroxy-6,7- dimethoxyflavone
Acacetin 7- 4'- trimethylether	5 hydroxy -7,4'- dimethoxyflavone
Santin	5,7-Dihydroxy-3,6,4'- trimethoxyflavone
6 Hydroxy kaempferol – trimethyl ether	6 Hydroxy– 3,6,7 trimethoxy flavone
Kaempferol 3 – methyl ether	5,7,4'Trihydroxy-3- methoxyflavone

TRADITIONAL USES^[11]

The specific part of this plant is used to treat specific diseases. Leaves of this plant used as a medication to treat many ailments such as itching, rash, swelling, rheumatoid arthritis, bone disorders, GI disorder and the muscle relaxant. Roots are used to treat headache. However, the mixtures of leaves and roots as paste are used to treat dental pain, headache, indigestion, diarrhea, and constipation.

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES**ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY**

Fasted rats were divided into 3 groups of six rats each. Group I served as a control, received distilled water. Group II – III received aqueous ethanol and butanol extracts respectively at a dose of 250 mg/kg body weight as a fine aqueous suspension orally. The rats of all groups were given glucose (2 g/kg body weight) 30min after administration of the drug. Blood samples were collected from the tail vein just prior to glucose administration and at 30 and 90 min after the glucose loading. Serum was separated and blood glucose levels were measured immediately by glucose-oxidase method.^[12]

ANTI-MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

The agar well diffusion method was used for the determination of antibacterial activity of the plant extracts. Every 100ml of cultured media were inoculated with 1ml of bacterial inoculum

(containing 1.5×10^8 cell/ml). After proper homogenization it was poured into Petri dishes. Thereafter, wells were made by using sterilized cork borer (10mm). Then the extracts were introduced into the wells, and ethanol 80% was used as control. The plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C . The experiment was performed three times and the activity of plant extracts was determined by measuring the diameter of inhibition zone around each well by millimeter.^[13]

ANTI-OXIDANT ACTIVITY

Total reducing power of *D. viscosa* extracts was performed by using procedure given below. The eppendorf tubes containing 0.2 ml of test sample (4 mg/ml DMSO), 0.4 ml of phosphate buffer (0.2 mol/l, pH 6.6) and 0.5 ml of potassium ferricyanide (1% w/v) were incubated at 50°C for 20 min. Then 0.4 ml of trichloroacetic acid (10% w/v) was incorporated and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min. From the centrifuged mixture, 150 μl of supernatant was transferred to 96 well plate containing 50 μl of ferric chloride (0.1% w/v). Absorbance was recorded at 630 nm. DMSO and ascorbic acid (1 mg/ml) at final concentrations of (0–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were used as negative and positive control. Total reducing power was computed using ascorbic acid calibration ($y = 0.0559x - 0.014$, $R^2 = 0.994$) and results were expressed as number of microgram equivalents of ascorbic acid per milligram of dry plant weight ($\mu\text{g AAE /mg DW}$) after triplicate analysis.^[14]

ANTI-HELMINTIC ACTIVITY

The anthelmintic potential of *D. viscosa* was studied by collecting Indian adult earthworms (*P. posthuma*) from a muggy area and rinsing with freshly prepared normal saline to eliminate all fecal matter and dust materials. The earthworm, approximately 5–7 cm in length and 0.3–0.5 cm in width were utilized for all the experiments. The concentrations of 12, 24, 36, and 48 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of all extracts were prepared for the bioassay, wherein the paralytic time and death rate are measured. Albendazole was used as a standard reference drug for positive control, and saline water was used as a negative control. The time taken to paralyze or individual death of worms was observed. The mean paralytic time was observed when there was no movement of any kind except when the worms were intensely shaken. The worms are observed that the shaken or given external stimuli, the paralyzing time was recorded.^[15]

WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

The rats were anesthetized before and throughout the wound infliction. The animals' dorsal fur was shaved using an electric clipper. The animals were randomly divided into four groups

($n = 6$). Group I served as the control (ointment base alone), whereas Group II served as the standard (5% w/w povidone iodine ointment). Groups III and IV were given DVFO at 2.5% and 5.0% w/w, respectively. Using a sterile scalpel, a 6 cm long and 2.1 mm wide incision wound was made on the shaved skin. Following the incision, the skin was held together and sewn at 1 cm intervals of interrupted sutures using a surgical thread and a curved needle (no.8). The wounds were left naked, and the formulations were topically administered to the wound daily. On day 8, the sutures were removed, and the formulation continued to be applied. On day 10, the breaking strength of the wound was tested using Lee's technique. Finally, the weight (in grams) required to break open the wound/skin, referred to as tensile strength, was measured.^[16]

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Mice were grouped (eight individuals) and Tissue Plasminogen Activator(2.5microgram) dissolved in acetone (20 microlitre) was applied on the internal and external surface on the right ear to cause edema. Doses of 3 mg/ear of each treatment were applied on the ear of each individual. For the isolated compound HA(Hauwatric Acid) doses of 0.25, 0.5 and 1.0 mg/ear were used. Reference anti-inflammatory drug was administered at 1 mg/ear. All treatments were dissolved in acetone and applied topically on both ears immediately after the administration of TPA. Six hours after administration of the inflammatory agent, the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation. Circular sections of 6 mm in diameter were taken from both: the treated (t) and the non-treated (nt) ears, which were weighed to determine the inflammation. Percentage of inhibition was obtained using expression below: Inhibition % = $[\Delta w \text{ control} - \Delta w \text{ treatment} / \Delta w]$ where $\Delta w = wt - wnt$; wt is the weight of the section of the treated ear; wnt is the weight of the section of the non-treated ear.^[17]

CONCLUSION

Plants are natural sources of bioactive compounds to treat various life-threatening diseases. *Dodonaea viscosa* has showed various phytochemicals which means that it can be used for treating diseases. The review shows the activity of various parts of the plant and its pharmacognostic profile. Extracts and Phytoconstituents isolated from this plant have shown to produce different pharmacological response which includes Anthelmintic, Antioxidant, Antibacterial, Antidiabetic, Anti-inflammatory, Wound healing Activity. Considering all the above medicinal importance of *Dodonaea viscosa* and it can be concluded that further studies on this plant may be helpful for future researchers to develop some new medicinal drugs.

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